

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AGYEMANG****FIRST NAME: NANA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: (MSWord Office 365 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
4. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40)
5. Latin abbreviations (EUCLID 2021, 59-64)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The coursepack ACA-401D Period 1 introduced me to the basics of academic writing. Contrary to what I have known to be acceptable, it presents a more standard, methodic, and acceptable doctorate-level style of writing.

In this response paper, I will discuss the appropriate structure of academic writing and how chosen language and style can impact the meaning or the idea intended by an author to their reader. Some of the concepts this paper shall focus on include punctuations and how they affect meaning, the academic wrongs of plagiarism, the use of standard Latin abbreviations, and style guide.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The overall framework of academic writing is very different from everyday fictional writing. Papers that are purposed for academic work employ stringent procedures such as researching and thinking through a topic, defining the question the topic presents, and analyzing and offering answers to the question (EUCLID 2021, 7).

To obtain sound evidence to support the answer to the question your paper tries to answer, thorough research into the topic must be done. The study would provide the knowledge and understanding needed to build your writing. The process requires a lot of time reading on the subject from relevant and related sources and taking notes, which would become helpful during the development of your writing (EUCLID 2021, 8-9).

After extensive research, the idea becomes apparent, and the next step would be to write an essay plan to help develop the answer to the question and how the essay would be structured (EUCLID, 2021, 9). It is essential to produce the first draft according to the essay plan. The structure must have an introduction, body, and conclusion.

Appropriate referencing is crucial to every academic writing. Referencing acknowledges the sources of information, and the failure to do so when the work of another is used is known as plagiarism. In the interest of academic integrity, it is imperative to cite the sources of any outside sources used in the writing. This will be discussed in more detail in this paper.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

The actual or intended meaning of a sentence can easily be missing or, at best, obscured if the punctuation rules are not strictly adhered to. "His friend, Sam was his second", for example, may appear to be very correct to many. However, commas may not be used where defining information is used at the start of a sentence (EUCLID 2021, 19). Based on this rule, the correct sentence would be His friend Sam was his second. Also, do not use a colon when the two parts of a sentence are not logically connected. For example, I used to be slim: I will try to lose weight. This cannot be correct as the two parts are not logically connected. An example of one that would be correct under the rule is I would like to be slim: I would try to lose weight.

Commas may not be used to join two main clauses or those linked by adverbs or adverbial clauses. Either use a semi-colon or add a coordinating conjunction. For example, Shakespeare was popular, and his plays were all profitable (EUCLID 2021, 19). Also, only one of the punctuations, such as full stops, exclamation marks, or question marks, must be used at the end of a sentence. For example, go home now! It would be wrong to say: go home now! (EUCLID 2021, 22).

4) PLAGIARISM

Using relevant or helpful information from a source in a piece of writing without acknowledging the source of that information is known as plagiarism. This is an unacceptable and unethical academic wrong. An example of plagiarism would be taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit (EUCLID 2021, 34). To avoid such a violation, every information used from the work of another in writing must be properly acknowledged through citation.

There are two types of referencing: in-text citations and list of work citations. For this response paper, I will focus my discussion on in-text citations. Citing the source of information or work used within the writing itself is known as in-text citation. For example, “Relativity’s theoretical foundations can be traced to earlier work by Faraday and Maxwell” (Einstein 782). In this example, the citation shows the name of the author and the page of the quote in parentheses.

Quotations and paraphrases are some common things that can be cited in writing. Quotations are the exact words of the author. Quotation marks must be used to capture the exact words of the author (EUCLID 2021, 35). For example, “Relativity’s theoretical foundations can be traced to earlier work by Faraday and Maxwell” (Einstein 782). However, long quotations adopt a different style of citation. Quotations that are over four lines would be treated as long quotations. Here, no quotation marks are required. The quotation would be indented and look like separate paragraphs (EUCLID 2021, 35). For example, in his poem “My Papa’s Waltz,” Theodore Roethke explores his childhood with his father:

The whiskey on your breath
Could make a small boy dizzy;
But I hung on like death:
Such waltzing was not easy.
We romped until the pans
Slid from the kitchen shelf;
My mother’s countenance
Could not unfrown itself (Purdue University 2023)

Citations are not required when the information being used is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas. For example, smoking causes lung cancer (EUCLID 2021, 37).

5) STYLE GUIDE

An author’s writing guide is the consistent approach he or she chooses to present the writing. Although many great writers advocate the use of individual preference in writing as opposed to the strict adherence to style guides, I find style guides provide a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output. Technical writers, for example, will generally have a style guide for a particular customer or project to ensure that the data they deliver will be in an acceptable form and will be in keeping with previous deliveries or other publications that the customer already has (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Unlike the rules of punctuation, which have general acceptance, style guides continue to be an issue of debate. Style comes in various forms, such as sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of the subject, US or UK spelling, readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, use of symbols, voice preferences, structure, etc...

From the forms of style guides listed above, it is doubtful that a creative writer would be bothered, whereas an academic research writer would have to consider all the forms (EUCLID 2021, 41-42). However, using style guides in academic writing provides the consistency and layout that sets it apart from creative writing.

6) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

Although the use of Latin abbreviations is generally acceptable in writing, it is strongly advisable to use the English equivalent of those abbreviations. This helps to prevent miscommunication or misunderstanding, especially in formal or technical writing. It is best to communicate clearly to your readers by avoiding Latin abbreviations, especially when their English equivalent would provide the same meaning and clarity.

Plain language is writing that is simple and direct. Avoid acronyms and abbreviations when writing in simple language, and rather use short sentences with simple words. In the first reading, plain language sustains the interest of the reader more than writing that has jargon and Latin abbreviations in its first few lines (EUCLID 2021, 59).

7) CONCLUSION

Following the standards and rules of academic writing enables the writer to present a more structured type of writing. Writing that has consistency in style, effective use of punctuations that provide clarity in meaning, and acknowledgment of every source of information used in the writing. This is why I find the introduction to international academic writing particularly important in this academic pursuit. I am very confident the requirement for periodic response papers would hone my writing skills in ways commensurate with the overall expectations of the program.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Purdue University. n.d. "MLA Formatting and style guide." Accessed November 21, 2023. https://owl.purdue.edu/owl/research_and_citation/mla_style/mla_formatting_and_style_guide/mla_formatting_quotations.html.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.